

**An exploratory study of human resource aspects of international technology transfers to
Sri Lankan private sector manufacturing firms**

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Purpose: To explore project-level human resource aspects of international technology transfers into private sector manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach: The study collected data from 35 international technology transfer projects. A self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the main mode for data collection. In addition to descriptive statistics, exploratory factor analysis and multiple regression were used to analyse data.

Findings: Firms have acquired product, process, and management-system technologies from countries having different institutional environments, namely, USA, Europe, China, Japan, and India. It was found that the country from which technology was sourced and the type of technology predict several project-level human resource aspects explored in this study.

Originality/value: The acquisition of human resource capabilities provides the central underpinning in international technology transfers. There is a marked absence of research-led literature on technology transfers at the project-level that resulted in less developed countries in Asia.

Keyword(s): Human resource, International technology transfer, Manufacturing industry, Sri Lanka.

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

International technology transfer (ITT) covers international transfer of all forms of physical assets, knowledge and human capabilities for the manufacture of a product, for the application of a process, or for the rendering of a service (Di Benedetto *et al.*, 2003; UNCTAD, 1979).

Firms in developing countries find that internal development of technology needed for new products, new processes, and operational improvement is fairly difficult. They must increasingly acquire technology from external/foreign sources (Lall, 1995; Medcof, 2007; Ming and Xing, 1999). Hence, technological progress in developing countries relies heavily on imported technology, which is based on the transfer, absorption and adaptation of existing knowledge

(Ming and Xing, 1999). The success of technology transfer, implementation and utilization, however, very much relies on internal capacity to absorb and accumulate foreign knowledge by technology acquirers (Barbosa and Vaidya, 1997; Stock and Tatikonda, 2000, 2004). Hence, at the project-level, the impact of transferring any type of technology on workforce and workplace is highly contested. However, extant literature on project-level technology transfer provides little guidance on human resource related aspects of ITT in recipient firms.

Understanding human resource aspects of ITT in an Asian less developed country is important for several reasons. First, though considerable amount of literature addressed ITT, those are mainly concentrated on areas such as the appropriateness of imported technologies, government policy on ITT, and business environment and investment climate of recipient countries (Ganesan and Kelsey, 2006; Hahm *et al.*, 1994; Medcof, 2007; Ming and Xing, 1999). Though such literature provides a sense of the overall technology transfer process, particularly at the strategic or national level, success of ITT is highly sensitive to project work-level human resource capabilities in dealing with new technologies acquired through ITT. It is against this backdrop that this paper presents a project-level analysis of ITT into private sector manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. Second, extant literature highlights the difficulties in ITT when technology is acquired from a country that has different institutional environment than the recipient country (Munir, 2002; Reddy and Zhao, 1990). Especially, internal diffusion of the gained technology thereafter has nonetheless to overcome numerous hurdles, and some of these hurdles are specific to less developed countries (Ganesan and Kelsey, 2006). Third, most of the extant literature on technology transfer has been directed to investigate areas such as learning and knowledge transfer, and spillover benefits that are resulted in during a technology transfer project; those were conducted in the Western world (e.g. Daghfous, 2004; Leonard-Barton, 1995; Mowery *et al.*, 1996). However, it has been suggested that the greatest impact of ITT is on the project-level activities and capabilities of employees to meet the new requirements (Grant and Gregory, 1997; Osman-Gani and Jacobs, 2005). However, little empirical research has been found to explain human resource aspects of ITT, particularly when it occurs in organisations located in less developed countries in Asia.

In the above context, an exploratory study was conducted using survey-based approach in the private sector manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka to address project-level human resource aspects of ITT in terms of: What are the technological aspects emphasised during the technology transfer and experience had with the technology transferor? What are the employee related problems faced during the technology transfer and strategies used to overcome those? What are the project-level achievements with the technology transferred? The achievements sought by technology acquiring firms can be grouped into financial returns, technical improvement and strategic development; there is some overlap between these three areas (Bennett et al., 1999). However, this paper primarily focuses on tactical, project-related outcomes associated with the technology transfer process. Further, it is assumed that the country from which the technology was transferred and the type of technology would have a significant influence in explaining project-level human resource aspects of technology transfer. As detailed in the section on methodology, the sample of the study consisted of 35 technology transfer projects, for which technologies were sourced from different parts of the world, i.e., either from European countries, USA, China, Japan, or India. It is suggested that cultural orientations, which are reflected in areas such as time-orientation, decision-making processes, and attitudes towards work that exists in different technology source countries, can affect the ITT process (see Bhagat *et al.*, 2002; Grant and Gregory, 1997; Jiang et al., 2007; Kedia and Bhagat, 1988; Lawrence and Lewis, 1993). Therefore, it is assumed that there would be significant differences in explaining project-level human resource aspects of technology transfer by the country from which technology is sourced.

Furthermore, the type of technology sourced for these 35 technology transfer projects can broadly be classified into either product, process or management-system (such as Toyota production system and total quality management) technologies. It is suggested that each of these technology types are quite different and may raise different issues in transfer, implementation and utilization (Ebrahimpour and Schonberger, 1984; Grant and Gregory, 1997; Lawrence and Lewis, 1993; Stock and Tatikonda, 2004). Therefore, it is assumed that there would be significant differences in explaining project-level human resource aspects of

technology transfer by the type of the technology acquired. It is expected that the findings of this study will provide a better understanding of project-level human resource aspects of ITT results in a less developed South Asian country, Sri Lanka in particular. Consequently, the findings of this exploratory study will be able to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area. In order to provide the context for the article, in the next section, relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background

The process of managing the acquisition and incorporation of technology from a source, external to the firm, is referred as technology transfer (Munir, 2002; Stock and Tatikonda, 2000); foreign direct investment and licensing agreements are major channels for importing technology (Ming and Xing, 1999; Olayan, 1999). Extant literature differentiates between product, process and management-system technologies. Product technology is the technology associated with the design of a product, usage and maintenance of the product, and the development of managerial and organisational capabilities needed to leverage the technology optimally. Process technology is the set of ideas involved in the manufacture of a product, or sequential steps and decisions necessary to combine/process materials to produce the finished product, technology associated with the maintenance of the process, and the development of managerial and organisational capabilities needed to leverage the technology optimally (Lall, 1995; Medcof, 2007). Stock and Tatikonda (2008, p65) identify this process of acquiring technology from a source outside the firm and its incorporation into a new or existing operational process (or process innovation) as external technology integration. Management-systems include new methods of organisation and management introduced to enterprises, such as total quality management, total productive maintenance, and Toyota production system (see Ahluwalia, 1997; Aoki, 2008; Barad, 1995; Gosen *et al.*, 2005; Jagadeesh, 1999; Im and Lee,

1989; Krasachol and Tannock, 1999; Sugimori et al., 1977; Voss, and Robinson, 1987). Extant literature suggests that different approaches might be needed to integrate different types of technology (Stock and Tatikonda, 2004).

In the context of technology transfer, Stock and Tatikonda (2004, p647) define technology uncertainty as the difference between the level of knowledge required by the recipient organisation to acquire and implement the technology, and the level of knowledge the recipient actually possesses, and represents the quantity of knowledge or information that must be acquired and processed. Stock and Tatikonda (2000, 2004) synthesise elements that contribute to technology uncertainty into three subdimensions, i.e., technology novelty, technology complexity, and technology tacitness. Technology novelty is “the degree of prior experience with the technology and the degree of change in the technology relative to prior technologies” (Stock and Tatikonda, 2004, p648). Technology complexity is “the level of interdependence between components in the technology, level of interdependence between the technology and elements external to it, and the scope of the technology” (Stock and Tatikonda, 2004, p648). The tacitness of the technology is “the tacitness of the knowledge embodied by the technology, and includes the degree, to which the technology is physically embodied, codified, and complete” (Stock and Tatikonda, 2004, p648). According to Stock and Tatikonda (2004) these three subdimensions represent largely different concepts; nonetheless, they overlap to some degree (p648). Higher levels of each subdimension increase the level of technology uncertainty and in turn increase the information processing requirements (Stock and Tatikonda, 2000, 2004). However, technology uncertainty is organisation-specific. Different levels of experience or absorptive capacity (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990) may mean that what is highly uncertain to one organisation may not be for another (Stock and Tatikonda, 2004).

The technology transfer benefits at the recipient firm can be grouped into financial returns, technical improvement and strategic development (Bennett et al., 1999). For instance, technology transfer is expected to generate increased financial returns through greater and/or increased sales; some of the technical improvements that can be gained include technical performance of the technology transfer based products, consistency, processing productivity,

and ease of use and maintenance; strategic development includes the attainment of a strong and stable market position, acquiring operational and development capabilities, and gaining a technical and market lead over competitors (see Bennett et al., 1999). Further, it has been suggested that there is some overlap between the financial, technical and strategic objectives (Bennett et al., 1999). This paper primarily focuses on project-related outcomes associated with the technology transfer process. Key elements of project-level outcomes are identified as time, cost and technical performance (Stock and Tatikonda, 2004). Further, these three elements make up three subdimensions of technology transfer project effectiveness, i.e., the functional operation of the technology (analogous to technical performance), technology transfer-related costs, and the time taken to complete the technology transfer project (Stock and Tatikonda, 2004).

However, technology transfer benefits are always associated with costs and risks of technology transfer (Bennett et al., 1999; Cannice *et al.*, 2003). The main types of project-level operational costs and technical risks associated with technology transfer have been identified in previous studies (e.g. Bennett et al., 1999). Some of the operational costs related to the actual implementation of the technology transfer include additional costs of development or adaptation of the technology, and manufacture and supply of components or sub-assemblies to the acquirer (Bennett et al., 1999). Technical risks are connected to the ability of the acquirer to absorb the technology and use it effectively to produce the final product to the required specifications (Bennett et al., 1999).

In this regard, the knowledge aspect of technology transferability has a number of implications for the selection of training resources and appropriate training methods, such as face-to-face training, on-the-job training, videos, documentation transfer, and visits to the home site by appropriate personnel (Grant and Gregory, 1997). Therefore, technology transfer-specific training has been identified as one of the main facilitators in transferring soft technology and building the host's capabilities for the successful transfer of technology (see Campbell and Vousden, 2003; Grant and Gregory, 1997; Osman-Gani and Jacobs, 2005; Sambasivarao and Deshmukh, 1995). It is expected that employees involved in the technology transfer project

would be able to apply new knowledge, skills and attitudes learned from technology transfer-specific training to the job and the subsequent maintenance of the learning on the job to increase project performance (Aoki, 2008; Kontoghiorghes, 2001).

Extant literature suggests that firms are continuously struggling to find ways to successfully introduce and manage technologies imported from countries that have different institutional environments than recipient countries (Howells and Michie, 1998; Lam, 1997). For instance, it is said that when technology is transferred from a firm from an industrialised country to a firm from a non-industrialised country, in part it could be influenced by large differences in technological development between the two spheres (see Boer et al., 1999; Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Gupta and Govindrajnan, 2000; Kim, 1998; Munir, 2002). On the other, it could be influenced by the wide variance that exists between the two contexts. When there are marked differences in the context of technology transferor and recipient firm, even if the technology fits with the proclaimed objectives of the organisation and sufficient resources are present to put it into operation, the recipient firm could face difficulties in achieving the level of performance that it promises (see Munir, 2002). In this regard, it is suggested that managers in many developing countries may hinder their ability to adapt to a foreign technology which requires a different and perhaps more advanced level of social understanding, which goes beyond the skills and knowledge required to use the technology (e.g. Aoki, 2008; Elsey and Fujiwara, 2000; Munir, 2002; Simonin, 1999). Whereas explicit elements that a technology represents is simpler to convey through import and replication of building designs, equipment, materials or software covering numerous facets of design and construction the implicit elements have to be learnt by recipient firms (Barret and Sexton, 2004; Bhagat *et al.*, 2002; Carrillo, 1996; Lall, 1995; Munir, 2002). This will create problems in the process of internalisation of new technologies at recipient firms (Kostova, 1999). Therefore, the acquisition of human capabilities provides the central underpinning in transfer, absorption and the usage of new technologies for the immediate efficient execution. However, it was also found that the language used for this process could act as a barrier and that facilitators from the technology transferor were unable to communicate the real meaning behind the words (see Elsey and Fujiwara, 2000). Therefore,

firms have to properly manage the transfer of gained technology in their entirety to new contexts; human resource plays the role as the main interface of technology transfer.

Though the majority of extant research studies on technology transfer were conducted from the home perspective, scholars have suggested the need of shifting the onus of technology transfer, implementation and utilization on to the host (e.g. Ebrahimpour and Schonberger, 1984; Grant and Gregory, 1997). However, literature on the ways in which firms in less developed countries address project-level human resource aspects to deal with new technologies acquired through ITT remains obscure.

Methodology

Population and sample

The Democratic Socialist Republic of Sri Lanka is an island in the Indian Ocean off the southeastern coastline of India with the population of 18.8 million, of which 47 percent were economically active in the census 2001 (Department of Census and Statistics, n.d.a).

The Department of Census and Statistics of Sri Lanka (n.d.b) classify industrial establishments operating in the country into three main divisions of Mining and Quarrying; Manufacturing; and the production and distribution of Electricity, Gas and Water according to the International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC) Revision - 3 of the United Nations (UN). The details of major industry divisions, the number of establishments operating in the country and number of persons engaged as at the year 2004 are presented in Appendix I. When value addition of the three major industrial divisions are considered, value addition of the manufacturing sector is over 85 per cent of the total value addition of the industrial sector (Department of Census and Statistics, n.d.c). The Department of Census and Statistics (n.d.c) classify manufacturing sector into nine subdivisions. Based on the number of establishments operating in the country and the number of persons engaged, the first four major manufacturing sectors of the country are food, beverages and tobacco; textile, wearing apparel and leather; non-metallic mineral products; and chemicals, rubber and plastic (Department of Census and Statistics, n.d.c).

In selecting the sample, we decided to concentrate on best performing manufacturing firms operating in the country as our intention was to explore project-level experiences of ITT. A sample of private sector manufacturing firms was identified that fulfilled the following selection criteria set for the study, 1) business performance of the firms. Published secondary data, such as annual reports and Colombo Stock Market performance were used to identify the best performing manufacturing firms of the country. Business performance criteria such as revenue growth, return on assets, growth of market share of the product segment, net profits, and profit to revenue ratio were evaluated; 2) a firm should have involved in at least one ITT project; 3) technology should be introduced to the production/manufacturing plant of the firm; 4) the introduced technology should be either a product, process or a management-system; and 5) the technology transferred should be in operation in the firm for at least 2 years. Of the 43 firms initially contacted, 35 firms agreed to participate in the survey. Hence, the study collected data on 35 technology transfer projects. To fulfil the expectations of this study, it was decided to collect data from the main person who has been in charge of a technology transfer process of a technology transfer project in each firm. Though this method of data collection has a limitation, in the absence of reliable research evidence, obtaining information from a “subject matter expert” is considered as a good starting point. When considering the education level of the respondents, all the respondents have either Bachelor’s degree or a postgraduate degree as the highest level of education.

The responded firms belong to food and beverages, fast moving consumer goods, wearing apparel, chemicals and pharmaceuticals, and plastic and rubber manufacturing industries. Though the Department of Census and Statistics (n.d.c) classify textile, wearing apparel and leather as one broad category of the manufacturing sector, we identified ITT occurrences that fulfil the above sample selection criteria only in wearing apparel firms. Further, in our sample, we identified several pharmaceutical item manufacturers. Those firms manufacture Western medicinal items or Aryurvedic/herbal medicinal items. Western medicinal item producers successfully cater for the local market while Aryurvedic/herbal medicinal item producers successfully cater for both local and export markets. When considering the number

of persons employed in the 35 firms selected for the study, 22 per cent had 100-500 employees, 40 per cent had 500-1000 employees, 32 per cent had 1000-1500 employees, and 6 per cent had more than 1500 employees. Though the Department of Census and Statistics (n.d.b) identifies manufacturing establishments with 10 persons engaged as the lower bound for medium scale establishments (lower bound for large scale establishments is not specified), the employee numbers in the firms in our sample are well above the lower bound of medium scale manufacturing establishments (refer to Appendix I).

Preliminary investigations of the authors led to identify that all these firms involved in technology transfers either to a) diversify into new products or markets, b) bring new or improved processes to increase the scale of existing activities, or c) move into up stream activities such as design/development, targeting either local market or export market. For example, food and beverages and fast moving consumer goods manufacturers cater for the local market while wearing apparel manufacturers cater for USA and European markets; some of the firms are trying to make a transition from “low-value added repetitive manufacturing” to being “high value added” to gain duty-free access to European market where Generalized System of Preferences (GSP+) is available. With regard to management-systems transferred, total quality management, lean production, Kaizen, six-sigma, Toyota production system, and total productive maintenance were identified. Further, technologies have been sourced either from USA¹ (about 7600 nautical miles away from Sri Lanka), Japan¹ (about 3700 nautical miles away from Sri Lanka), China¹ (about 2700 nautical miles away from Sri Lanka), India¹ (about 1300 nautical miles away from Sri Lanka) or from European countries¹, such as, Italy and Germany (about 4200 nautical miles away [Munich, Germany] from Sri Lanka). India is becoming a major technology transferor as technology transfers from India are supported by Indo-Lanka trade agreements. More details of the type of technology transferred and the country from which technology was sourced are given in the results section.

Measures

The areas covered in the self-administered questionnaire to address project-level ITT experiences were given below. Some of the question items were drawn from extant literature such as Kontoghiorghes (2001), Osman-Gani and Jacobs (2005), and Munir (2002) while others were constructed by the two authors based on the insights gained during the preliminary investigations.

- The nature of technology acquired (scale: categorical- product, process, and management-system);

For the study purposes the technology is broadly classified into three types based on the extant literature- product, process and management-system technologies. Product technology is the technology associated with the design of a product, usage and maintenance of the product, and the development of managerial and organisational capabilities needed to leverage the technology optimally, without making major changes to the existing manufacturing process. Process technology is the set of ideas involved in the manufacture of a product, or sequential steps and decisions necessary to combine/process materials to produce the finished product, technology associated with the maintenance of the process, and the development of managerial and organisational capabilities needed to leverage the technology optimally. Management-systems include new methods of organisation and management imported to the firms, such as Toyota production system and total quality management.

- The country/region from which technology was sourced (scale: categorical- Europe, USA, China, Japan, and India);
- Emphasis given to technological aspects during the technology transfer (scale: 5= Very high ... 1= Very low);
- Experience had with the technology transferor (scale: 5= Strongly agree ... 1= Strongly disagree);
- Employee related problems faced during the technology transfer (scale: 5= Very high ... 1= Very low);

- Strategies used to overcome employee related problems (scale: 5= Most frequently used ... 1= Least frequently used);
- The influence of new technology on workforce capabilities (scale: 5= Strongly agree ... 1= Strongly disagree);
- Methods used for technology transfer-specific training (scale: 5= Most frequently used ... 1= Least frequently used);
- The effectiveness of the methods used for technology transfer-specific training (scale: 5= Most effective ... 1= Least effective);
- The nature of training transfer climate of the technology transfer-specific training (scale: = Always ... 1= Never);
- The project-level achievements with the technology transferred (scale: 5= Very high ... 1= Very low).

The study further sought to examine whether above dimensions are predicted by the country/region from which the technology was sourced and the type of technology.

Considering the literacy of the respondents and amenability of the research questions, the questionnaire was constructed in English language. It was pre-tested with a random sample of 10 persons that fit with the intended sample of the study prior to the distribution.

Methods of data analysis

Data was analysed using the SPSS programme. In addition to descriptive statistics, exploratory factor analysis and multiple regression analysis were used. In the data analysis, we first produced frequency distributions for each aspect of technology transfer. Second, internal consistency (standardised Cronbach's alpha) of the scale was examined to ensure measures were unidimensional. Inter-item correlation analysis was conducted for the each set of measurements belong to a particular construct; none of the items had score correlation sums less than 0.4.

Third, exploratory factor analysis was used to validate the dimensions. Principal-components factor analysis was used as the extraction technique and Varimax as the rotation method. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair et al., 1998). Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test statistics were calculated. The items of each factor were averaged to produce a factor score for the each factor. The list of the measurement items belong to the constructs of "strategies used to enhance employee relationship", "employee capabilities and resource allocation for technology transfer-specific training", and "methods used to validate and evaluate training" were converged into several factors. The standardized estimates and reliability statistics for these constructs are presented and discussed in the results section, where appropriate. These details for the measurement items of other constructs that were converged into single factors are provided in Appendix II.

Finally, multiple regression was run to identify whether technology transfer experiences are predicted by the country/region from which the technology was sourced and the type of technology, separately. In interpreting results, R-square (adjusted) statistic and standardized coefficients were used.

Results

The nature of technology transferred and experience with the technology transferor

Table I shows the country of the technology transferor and type of technology transferred. Of the 35 firms, 16 involved in process technology transfers. It is also evident that product and process technology transferors were either from European countries (namely, Germany, Italy, Denmark), India, China, USA, or Japan while management-systems were transferred only from Japan.

Insert Table I

With regard to technological aspects emphasised during the transfer, 4-item measure (refer to Appendix II) had a standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.684 and converged into a single factor explaining 53 per cent of the variance. The results of the regression analysis for this variable (among other things) are shown in Table II. The regression model for this variable accounts for 11 per cent of the variance ($\text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.108$, $F = 5.13$, $p < 0.05$). The coefficient estimate for Japan, the country from which technology was sourced, is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Further analysis of means led to identify that when the technology is sourced from Japan, firms emphasise obtaining very details of the technology itself compared to other countries.

Insert Table II

With regard to the experience had with the technology transferor, 5-item measure (refer to Appendix II) had a standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.659 and converged into a single factor explaining 63 per cent of the variance. The results of the regression analysis led to identify that this factor is not significantly explained by either the country from which the technology was sourced or the type of technology. However, though the converged factor is not significantly explained, the preliminary analysis using ANOVA, led to identify significant differences in one of the items of this measure, i.e., "technology transferor provides technology at a lower cost but keeps high margin on critical spares/future consultancies" across the country from which the technology was sourced suggesting that firms are more likely to face such a situation with European countries (Mean=4.17, S.D.=0.41) than India (Mean=3.10, S.D.=0.87) (results are not shown in a table).

Employee related problems faced during the technology transfer and strategies used to enhance employee relationship

With regard to the number of employees affected by the new technology, of the 35 firms, 66 per cent said less than 50 employees have been affected; 17 per cent said 50 to 99 employees

have been affected; 11 per cent said 100 to 499 employees have been affected; and 6 per cent said more than 500 employees have been affected (results are not shown in a table). With regard to the types of employees involved in the transfer process, managers (58%), engineers (70%), technical staff (64%), supervisors (78%) and operators (83%) were mainly involved (percentages do not total into 100 due to multiple answers; results are not shown in a table).

The study inquired into the employee related problems faced by the firms due to technology transfer using 5-item measure (refer to Appendix II), which had a standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.820 and converged into a single factor explaining 60 per cent of the variance. The results of the regression analysis led to identify that this factor is not significantly explained by either the country from which the technology was sourced or the type of technology.

With regard to strategies used by the firms to enhance employee relationship, 9-item measure had a standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.810. Principal-components factor analysis yielded a set of two factors, which explained 59 per cent of the variance. The results of the analysis are shown in Table III. The results of the regression analysis led to reveal that none of these factors are significantly explained by either the country from which the technology was sourced or the type of technology.

Insert Table III

The influence of new technology on skill availability, the acquisition of new skills and technology transfer-specific training

With regard to skill availability and recruitment, it was revealed that firms recruited new employees for reasons such as insufficient staff in number (20%), insufficient skills and knowledge with the existing employees (33%), and to overcome resistance (4%) (results are not shown in a table). With regard to ways in which firms have dealt with existing employees after new recruitments have been made, it was revealed that the provision of technology transfer-specific training (74%), voluntary retirement (18%) and transfer to some other

department/subsidiary (17%) are common (percentages do not total into 100 due to multiple answers; results are not shown in a table).

With regard to the responses on employee capabilities and resource allocation for technology transfer-specific training, 10-item measure had a standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.799. Principal-components factor analysis yielded a set of two factors, which explained 71 per cent of the variance. The results of the analysis are shown in Table IV. Of these two factors, Factor 1 was labelled as "Hiring and skill enhancement" and Factor 2 as "Resource allocation". The results of the regression analysis shown in Table II suggest that the regression model for "hiring and skill enhancement" accounts for 10 per cent of the variance (Adj. $R^2 = 0.103$, $F = 4.89$, $p < 0.05$). The coefficient estimate for Japan, the country from which technology was sourced, is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Further analysis of means led to identify that when the technology is sourced from Japan, firms highly emphasise the aspects addressed in this factor compared to other countries. However, the factor "resource allocation" is not significantly explained by either the country from which the technology was sourced or the type of technology.

Insert Table IV

We inquired into the nature of technology transfer-specific training provision and whether there were any changes to existing organisational policies and procedures. The results are shown in Table V. We have not constructed an item measure for these aspects but several questions were asked on a 5-point Likert type scale. With regard to the nature of technology transfer-specific training provision, it was found that training programmes are designed to be conducted as overseas training at the technology transferor's environment ($\bar{X} = 3.89$). It is also found that firms design their training programmes in such a way that technology transferor provides both overseas training at the technology transferor's environment followed by local in-house training at the transferee's environment ($\bar{X} = 3.09$). Further, firms design their training programmes to provide training only as local in-house training at the transferee's environment ($\bar{X} = 3.00$).

Furthermore, when the transferor is from a non-English speaking country, the firms prefer to have overseas training at the technology transferor's environment ($\bar{X} = 2.51$). It was also found that training programmes are conducted by an in-house expert who was trained abroad or newly hired locally ($\bar{X} = 2.51$). Firms also design their training programmes to be provided by the local agent of the technology transferor or an expert hired as a consultant as local in-house training ($\bar{X} = 2.69$). With regard to the duration of technology transfer-specific training, 20 per cent of the firms said those are less than 3 days of duration, 21 per cent said less than 5 days, and 25 per cent said between 10 days to 14 days (results of the training duration are not shown in a table).

Firms identify language and cultural differences as a barrier for effective technology transfer-specific training ($\bar{X} = 3.06$). With regard to the language of training, of the 35 firms, 11 said those are only in English language (31%), one firm said only in native language- Sinhalese (3%) while 23 firms said in English language with an in-house person facilitating as a native language interpreter (66%) (results are not shown in a table). Firms also change organisational policies and procedures to facilitate technology transfer ($\bar{X} = 2.86$).

As the items shown in Table V were not considered to represent a particular area of interest, regression analysis was conducted on each item, separately. The results of the regression analysis are also shown in Table V. It is found that the regression model for the item "overseas training at the technology transferor's environment" accounts for 18 per cent of the variance (Adj. $R^2 = 0.179$, $F = 8.43$, $p < 0.01$). The coefficient estimate for management-system technology is statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). Further, the regression model for the item "when the transferor is from a non-English speaking country, overseas training at the technology transferor's environment" accounts for 20 per cent of the variance (Adj. $R^2 = 0.196$, $F = 5.15$, $p < 0.05$). The coefficient estimates for Japan ($p < 0.05$) and China ($p < 0.05$) are statistically significant. Finally, the regression model for the item "to facilitate technology transfer organisational policies and procedures have been changed" accounts for 11 per cent of the variance (Adj. $R^2 = 0.105$, $F = 4.97$, $p < 0.05$). The coefficient estimate for Japan is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Insert Table V

With regard to methods used for technology transfer-specific training, the item measure (refer to Appendix II) had a standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.871 and converged into a single factor explaining 66 per cent of the variance. The results of the regression analysis led to identify that this factor is not significantly explained by either the country from which the technology was sourced or the type of technology.

The effectiveness of the methods used for technology transfer-specific training was also explored. The item-measure (refer to Appendix II) had a standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.768 and converged into a single factor explaining 56 per cent of the variance. The results of the regression analysis shown in Table II suggest that the regression model for this variable accounts for 23 per cent of the variance ($\text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.229$, $F = 11.08$, $p < 0.01$). The coefficient estimate for Japan, the country from which technology was sourced, is statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). Further analysis of means led to identify that when the technology is sourced from Japan, firms find the effectiveness of the methods used for technology transfer-specific training is high compared to other countries.

With regard to training transfer climate of the technology transfer-specific training, 7-item measure (refer to Appendix II) had a standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.980 and converged into a single factor explaining 91 per cent of the variance. The results of the regression analysis shown in Table II suggest that the regression model for this variable accounts for 12 per cent of the variance ($\text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.118$, $F = 5.56$, $p < 0.05$). The coefficient estimate for management-system technology is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Further analysis of means led to identify that when the type of technology transferred is a management-system, firms highly emphasise the aspects addressed in this factor compared to other types of technology.

The methods used to validate and evaluate training were measured using 6-item scale and it had a standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.776. Principal-components factor analysis yielded a set of two factors, which explained 69 per cent of the variance. The results of the analysis are shown in Table VI. Of these two factors, Factor 1 was labelled as "Evaluation methods" and Factor 2 as "Validation methods". The results of the regression analysis led to reveal that none of the factors are significantly explained by either the country from which technology was sourced or the type of technology.

Insert Table VI

Project-level achievements with the technology transferred

With regard the project-level achievements with the technology transferred, 6-item measure (refer to Appendix II) had a standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.798 and converged into a single factor explaining 51 per cent of the variance. The results of the regression analysis shown in Table II suggest that the regression model for this variable accounts for 21 per cent of the variance (Adj. $R^2 = 0.213$, $F = 10.20$, $p < 0.01$). The coefficient estimate for India, the country from which technology was sourced, is statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). Further analysis of means led to identify that when the technology is transferred from India (Mean=2.91, S.D.=0.87), firms find project-level achievements are low compared to other countries (Europe: Mean=3.69, S.D.=0.84; USA: Mean=3.55 S.D.=0.55; China: Mean=3.50, S.D.=0.61; Japan: Mean=3.98, S.D.=0.35).

Descriptive statistics and correlations for all the variables are shown in Table VII.

Insert Table VII

Table VIII provides a summary of the main findings.

Insert Table VIII

Discussion, concluding remarks and managerial implications

Whilst it is recognised that project-level human resource related aspects are critical for technology transfer and may raise different issues in transfer, implementation and utilization, there is a scarcity of empirical studies that attempted to investigate project-level human resource aspects of ITT, especially when technology transfer occurred in less developed countries. The study explored the ways in which manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka address some of the human resource aspects at the project-level to deal with new technologies acquired through ITT; analysed the findings at two levels- the country from which the technology was sourced and the type of technology.

Firms have acquired three varieties of technologies- product, process, and management-systems from countries having different institutional environments, namely, USA, Europe, China, Japan, and India. As there are differences in each of the technology types itself and technology sourced countries, it was found that the country from which technology was sourced and the type of technology predict several project-level human resource aspects explored in this study.

The firms have sourced all management-systems from Japan. When the technology is sourced from Japan, it significantly explains several project-level human resource aspects of ITT. First, when the technology is sourced from Japan, firms highly emphasise to obtain the details of the technology in terms of technical/operational performance of the system, information required to operate it to achieve the designed operation, know-why to realise and manage the technology, know-how needed for the best use of the technology, and accumulated knowledge and information needed to realise the full potential of the technology from the Japanese transferors' compared to other countries (refer to Appendix II). Previous research also identifies importance of quantity and quality (or richness) of information that must be processed in external technology integrations, and the need of purposeful information processing - generation, aggregation, transformation and dissemination of information- to

conduct technology transfer (see- Stock and Tatikonda, 2004). Second, when the technology is transferred from Japan, firms find the need of changing organisational policies and procedures to facilitate technology transfer compared to other countries (refer to Table V). In this regard, evidence from past research (see- Munir, 2002) also suggests that new technologies such as lean production is more likely to be successfully incorporated into an organisation, if the environment is changed in accordance with the requisite norms of the new technology. Third, when the technology is sourced from Japan firms highly emphasise hiring and skill enhancement of employees compared to other countries. For instance, firms find the need of hiring new employees with high levels of existing skills and knowledge on the technology concerned, and the provision of technology transfer-specific training for all affected employees in the department/section (refer to Table IV). Fourth, when the technology is sourced from Japan, firms find the effectiveness of the methods used for technology transfer-specific training is high compared to other countries (refer to Table II). Finally, firms find that when the transferor is from a non-English speaking country, specifically, Japan or China, the provision of technology transfer-specific training at the technology transferor's environment as important compared to other countries (refer to Table V).

Further, when the technology transferred is a management-system, it significantly explains several project-level human resource aspects of ITT. That is firms find the importance of providing overseas training at the technology transferor's environment when the technology transferred is a management-system compared to other types of technology (refer to Table V). Previous research also suggests the importance of providing exposure to socio-economic-cultural settings in which the technology is originated and that a possible proxy for familiarity could be the amount of time the recipient firm's employees spend in the socio-economic-cultural context where the technology is originated (see- Munir, 2002). Further, firms find the importance of training transfer climate- in terms of supervisors and co-workers strongly encourage the acquisition and use of any new relevant skills and behaviours, job utility of newly acquired skills and knowledge, creating an environment which emphasises innovation and competition, the use of monetary or non-monetary rewards for using newly acquired skills and

knowledge during the training- in connection to management-systems transfer compared to other types of technology (refer to Appendix II). This exemplifies the importance of social-system in establishing supportive climate in which users of new technology are encouraged to use newly acquired skills and knowledge at the workplace. Especially, supervisory and peer support became an important factor when the job requires more interaction with others, as in the case of self-managed work teams. It should be noted, however, that firms have sourced all management-systems from Japan.

With regard to other types of technologies- process and product- or other countries that predict project-level human resource aspects of technology transfer, the preliminary analysis of data using ANOVA led to reveal that though technology recipient firms make attempts to obtain information and technical support from transferors in connection to new technology, firms are more likely to experience that technology transferor provides technology at a lower cost but keeps high margin on critical spares/future consultancies when technology is transferred from European countries than from India. Previous research (see- Cannice *et al.*, 2003) also provides evidence that transferors wish to protect their stock of valuable technical knowledge and know-how by limiting its diffusion; tend to transfer peripheral or dependent technologies to limit this risk (see- Cannice *et al.*, 2003). However, considerable future research is necessary to derive conclusive evidence in this regard.

The study also inquired into some of the project-level outcomes such as the consistency of the operational efficiency and reliability with the new technology, the level of achievement compared to the design specifications, the level of increase in productivity, and satisfaction with the employees' level of confident in handling the new technology (refer to Appendix II). It was found that firms identify the project-level achievements with the new technology is low when it was sourced from India compared to other countries.

Limitations of the study and areas for future research

The limitations of this study should be acknowledged. Aspects investigated in the study were defined at higher levels of abstraction and not at the level of detail. Due to scarcity of available

previous empirical research investigating the variables explored in this study, we developed item-measures for this study. Therefore, the prevalence of survey instrument related problems have to be acknowledged. However, the validity of a measure cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional exploratory study. Further, the study relied on one main person who has been in charge of a technology transfer project of each firm to access information and used self-report measures. Hence, future research could extend data collection by including managers, engineers, supervisors, shop floor operators, human resource managers etc. those who actively involve in the technology transfer process; compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data.

This study has not explored information regarding specific objectives or motivation behind each technology that was transferred. Therefore, future research could investigate how objectives of a technology transfer project influence outcomes or the effectiveness of the project. The study also concentrated only on project-level tactical outcomes. The immediate financial benefits that firms could achieve and strategic benefits that may not occur immediately were excluded from this exploratory study. This also opens an area for future research.

The nature of organisational change due to transfer of any type of technology is both continuous and episodic as initial changes at the project-level are often followed by waves of organisational change that would be either political, social, cultural, economic or environmental. As an initial attempt, the study explored limited project-level variables. Therefore, on one hand, we have not explored, for instance, what changes were made to existing organisational policies and procedures, such as performance appraisal, reward systems, and organisation structure and reporting relationships. On the other hand, how such project-level changes interact with firm-level environmental factors, such as culture, in which the transfer took place. Therefore, future research could be designed to address project-level as well as firm-level variables.

Note: ¹ the relative geographic distance was from: <http://www.worldatlas.com/aatlas/infopage/howfar.htm> (Accessed 12th October 2009).

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Tables

Table I: The country of the technology transferor and type of technology transferred

Country/region	Type of technology						Total	
	Product		Process		Management		N	%
	N	%	N	%	N	%		
Europe	2	16.3	4	25.0	-	-	6	17.1
USA	4	33.3	-	-	-	-	4	11.4
China	-	-	6	37.5	-	-	6	17.1
Japan	1	11.1	1	6.3	7	100	9	25.7
India	5	41.7	5	31.3	-	-	10	28.6
Total	12	100	16	100	7	100	35	100

Table II: Regression analysis

Dependent variable	Type of technology			Country/region					Overall R^2	Overall adjusted R^2	Overall F
	Product	Process	Management	Europe	USA	China	Japan	India			
Emphasis given to technological aspects during the technology transfer		S.S.M. not derived		0.002	0.012	0.069	0.367*	0.062	0.135	0.108	5.13*
Hiring and skill enhancement		S.S.M. not derived		0.051	0.150	0.167	0.359*	0.030	0.129	0.103	4.89*
Effectiveness of the methods used for technology transfer-specific training		S.S.M. not derived		0.112	0.151	0.169	0.501**	0.067	0.251	0.229	11.08**
Training transfer climate of the technology transfer-specific training	0.020	0.045	0.380*			S.S.M. not derived			0.144	0.118	5.56*
Project-level achievements with the technology transferred		S.S.M. not derived		0.023	0.112	0.136	0.143	0.486**	0.236	0.213	10.20**

Note: For each dependent variable, two separate multiple regression analyses were conducted, i.e., 1) by type of technology and 2) by country/region.

S.S.M. not derived = Statistically significant model not derived.

Standardised regression coefficients (betas) are reported.

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$; All other regression coefficients: $p > 0.10$.

Table III: Summarised results: strategies used to enhance employee relationship

	Factor 1: Strategies to enhance employee relationship1	Factor 2: Strategies to enhance employee relationship2
Negotiation and agreement	0.764	
Career planning	0.760	
Goal Setting	0.724	
Stress management programmes	0.669	
Team Building	0.607	
Facilitation and support		0.859
Employee participation and involvement		0.775
Creating a common vision		0.685
Communication and education		0.672
Explained variation	40.44%	18.23%
Eigenvalue	3.64	1.64
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	0.774	0.778
KMO sampling adequacy		0.690
Bartlett's Chi-Square		111.15***

Note: Standardised regression coefficients (betas) are reported.

*** $p < 0.001$.

Table IV: Summarised results: employee capabilities and resource allocation for technology transfer-specific training

	Factor 1: Hiring and skill enhancement	Factor 2: Resource allocation
The level of general education and training of employees helped to understand and absorb the technology transfer-specific training	0.880	
Organisation's continuous commitment for employee development plays a major role in preparing employees for the effective transfer of technology	0.870	
Design of the technology transfer-specific training programme is an important factor for the effective transfer of technology	0.854	
Proper assessment was made to find the gap between available employee capabilities and required levels for the new technology	0.818	
The recruitment of new employees with high levels of existing skills and knowledge on the technology concerned helped to overcome the requirement for in-depth technology transfer-specific training	0.790	
To cope with new technology, new employees with high levels of existing skills and knowledge were recruited	0.772	
Technology transfer-specific training was provided for all affected employees in the department/section	0.582	
Recruited new employees with a certain level of existing skills and knowledge on the technology concerned but technology transfer-specific training was provided	0.518	
Budgetary allocations for technology transfer-specific training is sufficient		0.694
Time allocation for technology transfer-specific training is adequate		0.669
Explained variation	42.76%	28.63%
Eigenvalue	4.06	2.96
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	0.820	0.745
KMO sampling adequacy		0.661
Bartlett's Chi-Square		174.55***

Note: Standardised regression coefficients (betas) are reported.

*** $p < 0.001$.

Table V: Summarised results: technology transfer-specific training provision and changes to existing organisational policies and procedures

Dependent variable	Mean	S.D.	Regression results								Overall R^2	Overall adjusted R^2	Overall F
			Type of technology			Country/region							
			Product	Process	Management	Europe	USA	China	Japan	India			
Training was provided by the technology transferor [†] :													
Overseas training at the technology transferor's environment	3.89	0.93	0.161	0.169	0.451**					S.S.M. not derived	0.203	0.179	8.43**
Overseas training at the technology transferor's environment and local in-house training	3.09	1.09			S.S.M. not derived					S.S.M. not derived	-	-	-
Local in-house training	3.00	0.90			S.S.M. not derived					S.S.M. not derived	-	-	-
When the transferor is from non-English speaking country, overseas training at the technology transferor's environment	2.51	1.22			S.S.M. not derived	0.075	0.165	0.365*	0.444*	0.125	0.243	0.196	5.15*
Training was provided by an in-house expert who was trained abroad or newly hired locally [†]													
Training was provided by the local agent of the technology transferor or an expert hired as a consultant [†]	2.69	0.93			S.S.M. not derived					S.S.M. not derived	-	-	-
Language and cultural differences become a barrier for effective technology transfer-specific training ^{††}	3.06	0.90			S.S.M. not derived					S.S.M. not derived	-	-	-
To facilitate technology transfer organizational policies and procedures have been changed ^{††}	2.86	1.11			S.S.M. not derived	0.071	0.125	0.123	0.362*	0.121	0.130	0.105	4.97*

Note: [†] 5= Most frequently used ... 1= Least frequently used.

^{††} 5= Strongly agree ... 1= Strongly disagree.

For each dependent variable, two separate multiple regression analyses were conducted, i.e., 1) by type of technology and 2) by country/region.

S.S.M. not derived = Statistically significant model not derived.

Standardised regression coefficients (betas) are reported.

* $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$; All other regression coefficients: $p > 0.10$.

Table VI: Summarised results: methods used to validate and evaluate training[†]

	Factor 1: Evaluation methods	Factor 2: Validation methods
Improvements in performance (such as production/running efficiency, quality of products)	0.872	
Calculate the level of wastage	0.825	
Evaluate the utilization of labour	0.813	
Feedback from participants		0.732
Feedback from supervisors		0.717
Feedback from resource persons		0.644
Explained variation	48.68%	20.48%
Eigenvalue	2.92	1.23
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	0.878	0.787
KMO sampling adequacy		0.714
Bartlett's Chi-Square		72.55***

Note: [†] 5= Most frequently used ... 1= Least frequently used

Standardised regression coefficients (betas) are reported.

*** p<0.001.

Table VII: Means, standard deviations and correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
1 Technological aspects ...	3.63	0.60	1.00														
2 Experience with transferor...	3.73	0.66	0.43**	1.00													
3 Employee problems	2.70	0.53	0.03	0.04	1.00												
4 Strategy to enhance employee relationship1	3.39	0.61	0.36*	0.63**	0.17	1.00											
5 Strategy to enhance employee relationship2	3.03	0.59	0.27	0.48**	0.02	0.42*	1.00										
6 Hiring and skills	3.74	0.60	0.32	0.54**	0.36*	0.42*	0.40*	1.00									
7 Resource allocation	2.79	0.64	0.16	0.06	0.14	0.01	0.10	0.22	1.00								
8 Overseas training ...	3.89	0.93	0.27	0.12	0.09	0.08	0.12	0.25	0.03	1.00							
9 Overseas training-transferor non-English ...	2.51	1.22	0.49**	0.51**	0.02	0.31	0.46**	0.30	0.09	0.49**	1.00						
10 Policies/procedures changed	2.86	1.11	0.19	0.04	0.32	0.08	0.32	0.23	0.22	0.10	0.07	1.00					
11 Training methods	2.57	0.84	0.38*	0.08	0.28	0.21	0.22	0.01	0.47**	0.16	0.14	0.61**	1.00				
12 Effectiveness-training methods	2.66	0.88	0.34*	0.04	0.22	0.09	0.31	0.01	0.24	0.09	0.32	0.52**	0.70**	1.00			
13 Training transfer climate	2.72	1.41	0.11	0.06	0.16	0.07	0.09	0.25	0.31	0.01	0.25	0.23	0.43*	0.38*	1.00		
14 Training evaluation	3.54	0.92	0.42*	0.42*	0.00	0.18	0.26	0.54**	0.29	0.38*	0.15	0.09	0.03	0.18	0.11	1.00	
15 Training validation	2.92	1.29	0.32	0.30	0.34*	0.28	0.33*	0.47**	0.04	0.11	0.17	0.17	0.30	0.25	0.20	0.43**	1.00
16 Project-level achievements	3.47	0.86	0.51*	0.65**	0.15	0.49**	0.44**	0.77**	0.33*	0.09	0.23	0.15	0.12	0.08	0.24	0.50**	0.45**

Note: * significant at 0.05 level.

** significant at 0.01 level.

Table VIII: Summary of main findings

Dependent variable	Country/region					Type of technology		
	Europe	USA	China	Japan	India	Product	Process	Management
Emphasis given to technological aspects during technology transfer, i.e., operational performance, know-how/why, accumulated knowledge, etc.				●				
Experience with technology transferor, i.e., in obtaining technical specifications, operating procedures, spares/future consultancies, etc.								
To facilitate technology transfer organizational policies and procedures have been changed				●				
Employee related problems faced during the technology transfer								
Strategies used to enhance employee relationship								
Hiring and skill enhancement				●				
Technology transfer-specific training provision:								
Overseas training at the transferor's environment								●
When the transferor is from non-English speaking country, overseas training at the transferor's environment			●	●				
Resource allocation for technology transfer-specific training								
Methods used for technology transfer-specific training								
Effectiveness of the methods used for technology transfer-specific training				●				
Training transfer climate of the technology transfer-specific training								●
Language and cultural differences become a barrier for effective technology transfer-specific training								
Methods used to validate and evaluate training								
Project-level achievements with the technology transferred					●			

Note: "●" indicates statistically significant coefficient estimate in regressions. A blank cell indicates no statistically significant coefficient estimate in regressions.

Appendix

Appendix I: Industrial establishments and number of persons engaged as at the year 2004

Major divisions	Number of establishments [†]					Number of persons engaged ^{††}				
	Total	Small industries [‡]		Medium and large industries ^{‡‡}		Total	Small industries [‡]		Medium and large industries ^{‡‡}	
	F	F	%	F	%	F	F	%	F	%
Mining and Quarrying	6,248	5,413	4.5	835	8.4	36,948	21,378	7.5	15,570	2.1
Manufacturing[◊]	124,351	115,351	95.0	9,000	90.3	990,348	262,716	92.0	727,632	97.3
Electricity, Gas and Water	788	657	0.5	131	1.3	6,155	1,453	0.5	4,702	0.6
Total	131,387	121,421	100	9,966	100	1,033,451	285,547	100	747,904	100

Manufacturing industry [◊]					
Persons engaged size class ^{††}		Establishments [†]		Persons engaged ^{††}	
		F	%	F	%
Small industries [‡]	1-4	104,046	83.7	192,859	19.5
	5-9	11,305	9.1	69,859	7.1
	Subtotal	115,351	-	262,716	-
Medium and large industries ^{‡‡}	10-19	4,316	3.5	55,676	5.6
	20-49	2,239	1.8	66,270	6.7
	50-99	1,043	0.8	69,986	7.1
	100 and above	1,402	1.1	535,700	54.1
	Subtotal	9,000	-	727,632	-
Total		124,351	100	990,348	100

Notes:

F= Frequency; %= Percentage

[†] Establishment characteristics- Availability of its own production facilities; maintaining of accounts pertaining to the establishment; and availability of distinct management and a suitable location.

^{††} Number of persons engaged includes working proprietors, active partners, unpaid family workers, operatives and all other employees.

[‡] Less than 10 persons engaged

^{‡‡} 10 and more persons engaged.

[◊] Manufacturing establishment: Conversion of something or part into another by using chemical or mechanical process. This can be done by machines or labour force.

Source: Department of Census and Statistics of Sri Lanka (n.d.b)

Appendix II: Measurement items for each construct that converged into single factors
Figure in parenthesis after each item given below denotes standardized estimate.

Emphasis given to technological aspects during the technology transfer

(Standardized Cronbach's alpha=0.684; KMO sampling adequacy=0.670; Bartlett's Chi-Square and significance=27.71, $p<0.001$; Eigenvalue=2.12; Explained variation=52.96).

- Technical/operational performance of the system and information required to operate it to achieve the designed operation (0.870)
- Know-why which includes knowledge, skills and experience of individual human beings or groups to realise and manage the technology (0.816)
- Know-how such as processes, techniques, methods, pertinent facts, and relationships such as those described in publications, documents, blue prints, etc. needed for the best use of the technology (0.749)
- Accumulated knowledge and information needed to realise the full potential of the technology which is embodied in the above three components (0.703)

Experience with technology transferor

(Standardized Cronbach's alpha=0.659; KMO sampling adequacy=0.594; Bartlett's Chi-Square and significance=47.27, $p<0.001$; Eigenvalue=1.88; Explained variation=62.79%).

- Proper negotiations were made to obtain all the required technical specifications, standard operating procedures, operation and repair manuals that included all important design details, training, etc. (0.927)
- Proper negotiations were made to obtain all functional requirements of the technology (0.901)
- Technology provider deliberately hide critical operational and design related information about the technology (0.716)
- Technology provider did not provide all operational and repair manuals, to restrict the understanding of the technology (0.702)
- Technology provider gives technology at a lower cost but keeps high margin on critical spares/future consultancies (0.626)

Employee related problems faced during the technology transfer

(Standardized Cronbach's alpha=0.820; KMO sampling adequacy=0.718; Bartlett's Chi-Square and significance=61.65, $p<0.001$; Eigenvalue=2.93; Explained variation=59.76%)

- Resistance from employees for the technology transfer project (0.857)
- Unwillingness of the employees to learn the new technology (0.818)
- Fear of losing recognition due to new technology (0.801)

- Employees feel stressful (0.711)
- Fear of job loss due to new technology (0.621)
- Communication problems between management and operator level employees ^a

Methods used for technology transfer-specific training

(Standardized Cronbach's alpha=0.871; KMO sampling adequacy=0.733; Bartlett's Chi-Square and significance=110.46, $p < 0.001$; Eigenvalue=3.31; Explained variation=66.21).

- Workshops- non-residential (0.851)
- Class room/Lectures (0.846)
- Workshops- residential (0.838)
- Audio and video tapes (0.799)
- Self-instructional material (0.728)
- On-the-job training ^a
- Small group discussions ^a
- Games and simulation ^a

Effectiveness of the methods used for technology transfer-specific training

(Standardized Cronbach's alpha=0.768; KMO sampling adequacy=0.737; Bartlett's Chi-Square and significance=54.61, $p < 0.001$; Eigenvalue=2.73; Explained variation=56.63).

- Workshops- non-residential (0.890)
- Workshops- residential (0.815)
- Class room/Lectures (0.782)
- Self-instructional material (0.747)
- Audio and video tapes (0.523)
- On-the-job training ^a
- Small group discussions ^a
- Games and simulation ^a

Training transfer climate of the technology transfer-specific training

(Standardized Cronbach's alpha=0.980; KMO sampling adequacy=0.913; Bartlett's Chi-Square and significance=402.12, $p < 0.001$; Eigenvalue=5.47; Explained variation=91.23).

- Supervisors supported and encouraged the application of new skills and knowledge acquired during the training (supervisory support for new skills) (0.986)
- Users of the new technology received rewards (monetary or non-monetary) for using newly learned skills and knowledge acquired during the training (0.979)

- Users of the new technology functioned in a work environment which emphasised innovation and competition (innovative-competitive organisation) (0.977)
- Users of the new technology, who undergone training do not fear of using newly acquired skills and knowledge due to possibilities of making mistakes which could result in punishment (punishment consequences) (0.964)
- Characteristics of the job prompted/reminded users of the new technology to use new skills and knowledge acquired during the training (task cues) (0.910)
- Users of the new technology functioned in an environment in which supervisors and co-workers strongly encouraged the acquisition and use of any new relevant skills and behaviours (social support for new skills) (0.825)
- Users of the new technology motivate to use the newly acquired skills and knowledge when they see those cause to increase productivity, reduce errors, better problem solving, etc. (job utility) (0.820)

Project-level achievements with the technology transferred

(Standardized Cronbach's alpha=0.798; KMO sampling adequacy=0.629; Bartlett's Chi-Square and significance=80.77, $p < 0.001$; Eigenvalue=3.04; Explained variation=50.67%).

- The level of increase in productivity (0.839)
- Satisfaction with the employees' level of confident in handling the new technology (0.827)
- Consistency of the operational efficiency and reliability with the new technology (0.730)
- The level of achievement compared to design specifications (0.669)
- Improvements in employees' general attitude towards the new technology (0.598)
- Satisfaction with the degree of training (technology transfer-specific) transferred to the workplace (0.560)

Note: ^a the item was dropped during factor analysis